

GENERAL PRINCIPLES AND THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF PHYSICAL CULTURE AND SPORTS

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Abstract: *This article provides information on the general principles and theoretical foundations of physical culture and sports, the purpose of physical education and sports health activities, and a healthy lifestyle.*

Key words: *Physical education, sport, wellness, physical education, exercises, training, wrestling, swimming, athletics.*

INTRODUCTION

The purpose of physical education and sports rehabilitation activities is to teach students the requirements for physical development of their body and healthy lifestyle. At the same time, physical training, sports and wellness activities will greatly help in the positive assimilation of professional training.

Students' physical education events are in the form of morning physical education, physical education classes, sports club training, sports fitness competitions and holidays. Morning physical education classes for students it is performed independently in the bedroom, in the living room and in the family.

Morning physical training can consist of exercises for arms, legs and body muscles, breathing exercises. Physical education classes are organized according to the student curriculum. In physical education classes, students are trained in football, basketball, volleyball, and handball games. Also athletics, gymnastics, wrestling and swimming actions, skills and abilities are taught and formed.

Sports holidays and competitions on the agenda can include tourist walks, taking water treatments, swimming and bathing classes, competitions and competitions between groups. In training of sports clubs they will achieve specialization in sports. Students demonstrate their physical, technical and tactical training in sports competitions and sports holidays.

Also, methods of receiving training procedures of students under the influence of natural factors water, sun and air during tourism training were studied. Medical control of the physical development of students and the level of physical fitness in the processes of participation in physical education and sports, wellness activities assessment with practical tests was organized.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

In different directions, that is, whether it is a mathematician, a physicist, a historian or whether he is a physical education teacher, his work style is directly related to pedagogical activity. The meaningful and high-quality conduct of the lesson, in turn, is closely related to his pedagogical skill, pedagogical skills, pedagogical competence, and pedagogical activity in general. Famous Russian pedagogue V.A. Sukhomlinsky:

Morning physical education classes, physical education classes, sports clubs, sports holidays and competitions organized for students in educational institutions and places of residence, organized on weekends.

physical education and sports, wellness events organized in educational institutions are organized on the basis of the physical education program. Physical education programs of students age and gender indicators and physical body will be improved according to the levels of development. In physical education programs, the materials of physical education classes and the content of physical education extracurricular activities are based on modern requirements formed. At the same time, students are involved in physical education and sports, and physical education and sports in the processes of wellness activities having theoretical information about the positive effects of training on the body and the rules and requirements of independent exercise, natural factors of water, sun and air they go.

In providing such theoretical information, it is considered appropriate to widely use the literature and instructions of mature specialists of our country and foreign countries, as well as materials from the INTERNET.

Effective organization of physical training, sports and wellness activities in educational institutions and places of residence of students, as well as in the family, ensures that the future young generation of our country will be raised as a physically and spiritually mature person and become an active member of our society.

The theory of physical education is a scientific and practical science that analyzes the laws of physical culture. The main concepts of the theory of physical education: physical development, physical education, physical education system, physical maturity and physical culture. Through these concepts, the essence and basic laws of the theory of physical education are studied. They are constantly changing and expanding and reflecting deep content.

Physical development is the creation, change and improvement of biological forms and functions in the body under the influence of education. This process is subject to the laws of structure, change, quantity and quality changes of the organism and its habitat. As a result of social development, the production of physical characteristics, high results in the field of culture, science and sports made it possible to achieve. The natural vital forces and the structure of organisms passed from generation to generation are the basis for human physical development.

But the direction of physical development, its character, level, as well as a person the qualities and abilities that are perfected in themselves depend in many ways on the living conditions and upbringing. Mastering the laws of physical development, using them for the purposes of physical education - the theory and practice of physical education is an important task. People's social life conditions are of decisive importance in physical development. Among them, physical education plays the most important role plays.

A person's life activity is conscious, his actions have meaning and purpose. The new generation learned the activity from the previous generation, and between them, communication and continuity is established, which consists of teaching knowledge, skills and qualifications. Physical education to each other from the point of view of its own characteristics can be divided into two groups.

Today, the development of modern military equipment had great potential even without human intervention. Now, in the period when the threats of war are being eliminated, every person should protect himself, his family, and society with his own strength and courage. should be able

to protect. Therefore, special service units pay great attention to sports training. The training will be aimed at forming and improving the skills of single combat, survival in any conditions and movement in any places.

The principle of physical education to develop a person from all sides: In the process of physical education, there are great opportunities to solve the tasks of mental, moral and aesthetic education. Solving these tasks expands the role of physical education as a factor of all-round development of a person and directly ensures the success of physical education. Only people who have matured spiritually and physically in all aspects can be the builders of an improved society. Education of a perfect person takes place in the conditions of properly organized physical education. To be a well-developed person is a requirement of biological and social laws. A person's physical perfection is inextricably linked with his spiritual perfection. The spiritual world of a person is affected by external influences, social environment and it is formed due to the action of a person aimed at changing the surrounding conditions. It can be seen that the process of physical education is the physiological foundation for the formation and connection of conditioned reflexes.

A person's achievements in physical education and sports, records, high-level movement and skill formation gain value when they are inextricably linked with the athlete's mental, moral, spiritual, aesthetic and ideological-political formation. social activity is specialized and depends on production and military physical training, that is, the success of specialization is created on the basis of education and physical training. All-round general physical fitness is one of the main principles of human development. The improvement of physical qualities, the formation of high-level movement skills and abilities provides an opportunity to carry out special physical and sports training. The pursuit of records or ambition in sports violates the principle of physical education and sports comprehensive development of the individual, and as a result, unethical athletes are formed that are not suitable for society.

The principle of physical education health: The following rules are derived from this principle: Strengthening the health of those engaged in physical education.

Physical culture organizations, physical education teachers, trainers work with healthy people. They are not only for maintaining the health of those engaged in gymnastics, sports, games and tourism, but also for their they are also responsible for strengthening their health. Physical exercises are correct it has a healing effect under the conditions of use. Physical exercises Improper use can harm health. It is necessary to take into account the age, gender, biological characteristics and fitness of those who do physical exercises.

CONCLUSION

Physical education and sports, fitness classes conducted in educational institutions, sports clubs it is possible to include trainings, sports competitions and sports holidays, as well as mass organized tourism activities.

Sports training for physical education events outside the educational institution in the sports clubs of the sports school for children and teenagers training and physical education in places of residence, neighborhoods and family events were introduced. Training in sports circles is high in sports solves the tasks of training a qualified athlete. Physical education activities organized in the places of residence and in the family are aimed at the physical development of students, preparing them to become morally and morally competent people, as well as for work activities will be aimed at preparation.

Nature walks were organized in educational institutions under the guidance of physical education teachers and class leaders. In this, students should be trained in the formation of physical movement skills and abilities, training with the help of natural factors, development of physical qualities was carried out.

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